

A phosphorus and nitrogen containing halloysite derivative as multifunctional flame retardant for biobased polyamide 56

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Abstract

In this report, a biobased polyamide (PA56) was selected as the polymer matrix and halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) were chosen as the reinforcement material. By using a sustainable synthesis pathway, a biobased flame retardant complex formed by phytic acid (PhA) and chitosan (CS) was successfully grafted to the HNTs. The chemical structure of the modified HNTs was characterized by FTIR, while the surface morphology and dimensions were studied using TEM and SEM-EDX. After the introduction of 3 wt.% HNTs into the PA56 the TGA onset, peak degradation temperatures and residue were notably increased. The modified nanomaterials also provided higher tensile strength and elongation at break. Furthermore, the biobased FR exhibited a synergistic effect on fire properties performance. The peak heat release rate was decreased by 51% and the combustion times were also delayed more than 100 s. The significant increase in flame retardancy was attributed to the barrier effect of halloysite nanotubes and the catalytic carbonization induced by phytic acid during the formation of the char layer. The results of this study show that it is possible to enhance the flame retardant and mechanical properties of polyamide composites by using the combination of nanoclay and biobased flame retardant additives.

Keywords:

Flame retardant polyamide, halloysite nanotubes, Phytic acid, chitosan, Biobased polymer composites.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, many scientific research efforts have revealed the potential of biobased materials derived from natural resources like starch, cellulose and chitin owing to their lower environmental impact [1]. In the context of generating sustainable polymers from renewable resources, some biopolyamides such as PA-11 have been developed in the last decades and several interesting prospects with great potential have been studied in previous research reports. However, their feasibility in terms of performance, cost, sustainability and availability is currently in need of further validation in order to establish solid market solutions [2].

As polymers have become more prevalent in modern times, the inherent fire hazards have increased as well. In fact, every year fire accidents result in a great number of deaths and substantial financial damage worldwide [3]. Commercial plastic materials are mostly made of hydrocarbon chains. Consequently, when exposed to temperatures between 250 °C and 450 °C, the carbon bonds are broken and the polymers pyrolyze, releasing volatile gases [4]. The combustion process is sustained by the constant exposure of the flammable materials to the heat flow until the material burns completely and the flame fades out [5, 6]. By interfering with the burning cycle, flame retardant treatments applied to polymers can reduce the intensity of their burning. In previous research reports, flame retardants have been classified according to their chemical composition (halogen concentration, organic or inorganic), action mechanism (gas or condensed phase) or means of addition into a polymer (additive, reactive) [7, 8]. Other relevant investigations on different polymeric materials have also exposed the advantages of phosphorus-based FRs and their multiple effects after being introduced into different polymers via additive or reactive methods [9]. Several synergistic effects were revealed after the addition of metallic salts and polyphosphates into glass-fiber reinforced polyamide 6,6 displaying a remarkable flame retardant mechanism mainly based on a condensed phase action [10, 11].

Owing to the need to reduce fire risk and comply with fire safety regulations, biobased flame retardants are among the most hopeful green alternatives to halogenated flame retardants. Recently different researchers have proven phytic acid (PhA), or its salts, to be useful in different applications, its biological nature (along with its high phosphorus content 28 wt.%) has placed it under the spotlight of fire retardants research [12, 13]. One of the first reports of the modified phytic acid as flame retardant additive is related to the combination with chitosan via ionic bonding and complex formation, as part of the layer-by-layer assembly treatment applied to cotton fabric. The findings show that the self-extinguishing effect was achieved after applying the protective coating treatment to the fabrics. The phytic acid-chitosan polyelectrolyte complex was also added to an ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer and it was possible to improve the charring capacity of the composites by the simultaneous presence of phosphorus, nitrogen, and carbon [14, 15].

Chitosan (CS) has become one of the most promising possibilities for preparing functional polyelectrolyte complexes (PECs) due to its many benefits, including nontoxicity, biodegradability, and antibacterial action. In research field, many publications have recently investigated the potential addition of CS to flame retardant systems in the form of multilayer coating. The decomposition of CS during combustion has been reported to improve the carbon source and foaming mechanisms of flame retardant systems [16, 17]. Halloysite nanotubes (HNT) are formed by multiple-layered

tubes that are covered by aluminosilicate layers. The HNTs are frequently used as nanofillers for polymer matrices such as polyamide 6 and polyamide 12. More recently HNTs are also being employed as nanofillers for biopolymer materials like polylactic acid, polylactic acid/poly(-caprolactone), chitosan, polyethylene and others [18, 19]. The surface of HNTs has abundant oxygen atoms, making hydrogen bonding a simple method for creating multifunctional nanostructures via hybridization between different building blocks under mild conditions [20]. Phosphorus-containing flame retardants have been bonded to the surface of the HNTs, to improve the char formation capacity of polymers [21, 22]. To explore the flame retardant potential of HNTs and further expand their applications, the external layers of these tubular nanomaterials were often coated by phosphorus and nitrogen containing aggregates (e.g. Melamine, phytic acid and DOPO) obtaining significant improvements in terms of heat release and smoke production capacity of thermoplastic resins such as polypropylene or polylactic acid [23, 30].

Chitosan can interact with nanoclays considering the positive charge in aqueous solution, along with the amino and hydroxyl groups [24, 25]. Consequently, different approaches have been used to enhance the mechanical performance and thermal stability of nanocomposites taking advantage of the interfacial compatibility between the highly reactive amino groups of the polysaccharide and negatively charged clay particles [26, 27].

Surface modification of HNT is typically found necessary to increase the interfacial compatibility with polymers. For instance, a layered silver (Ag) and polyphosphazene (PZE) modified halloysite was created by incorporating silver particles first into HNTs and then using polyphosphazene to further modify the Ag@HNT nanocomposites, endowing the epoxy resin with higher flame retardancy featuring enhanced catalytic carbonization and barrier effects [28, 29]. Overall, it is believed that surface modification of HNTs with a polyelectrolyte complex formed by phosphorus-rich phytic acid and nitrogen-containing chitosan is crucial for enhancing flame retardancy of the biobased polyamide by increasing the charring capacity of the halloysite via the combined action of P, Si, Al along with the flame dilution effects provided by the nitrogen moieties contained in chitosan. Moreover, the application of organically modified HNT to polyamides requires further exploration, as the recent research trends are more oriented towards reducing the flammability of PA56 by using different methodologies such as the development of DOPO-derivatives by Michael addition for dip-coating functionalization of PA56 fabrics [30], the synthesis of flame retardant monomer 2-carboxyethyl(phenyl)phosphinic acid (CEPPA) or the itaconic acid pentamethylenediamine (ITDA) salt, which were introduced and copolymerized as reactive flame retardants into the polyamide 56 matrix [31, 32].

In this research, we aim to reveal the synthesis and characterization of a biobased flame retardant polyamide featuring increased mechanical properties and different flame retardant mechanisms as a consequence of the addition of a modified HNT filler, which was previously prepared by the introduction of P-N containing components such as phytic acid and chitosan. The thermal degradation, mechanical properties, and flame retardant performance, along with additional fundamental characterization, will unveil the potential of a polymer that is already being considered for different applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Halloysite Nanoclay (Kaolin aluminum silicate, hydrated) molecular weight (mw): 294.19 g/mol, density (d): 2.53 g/cm³. Phytic acid solution, 50 wt. % in H₂O, mw: 660.04 g/mol, d: 1.432 g/ml (25 °C). Chitosan with a mw: 1526.464 g/mol, viscosity: 20-300 cP, 1 wt. % in 1% acetic acid (25 °C), Acetic acid: reagent grade with a purity of ≥ 99%, mw: 60.05 g/mol, melting point (mp): 16.2 °C, d: 1.049g/ml (25°C) and Sodium hydroxide: reagent grade 97 %, d: 2.13g/cm³, M: 40 g/mol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Darmstadt, GE). Polyamide 56, biobased polyamide resin Ecopent 1273, Injection grade: relative viscosity: 2.76 cP (25 °C), mp: 255 °C was kindly provided by Cathay Industrial Biotech (Shanghai, CHN).

2.2. Modification of halloysite with phytic acid and chitosan

By following a slightly modified reaction pathway, HNT@PhA were prepared by in-situ synthesis: Initially, a three-necked flask was filled with 350 mL of deionized water and 5.83g of HNTs were slowly added, the temperature was fixed at 80 °C, and the dispersion was magnetically stirred for 10 minutes. Secondly, 10 g PhA were mixed with 30 mL deionized water and then added into the flask dropwise. The reaction was continued at 80 °C for 2h under ultrasonic treatment (500 watts, 20 kHz, amplitude of 20% and intervals of 5s). Finally, the suspension was filtered and washed 7 times with deionized water and then dried at 80 °C for 2 h [33].

The typical procedure for the chitosan addition was divided into dissolution and treatment of chitosan, and then reaction with HNT nanoparticles. First, 2g of chitosan were dissolved in 100 ml of 1M acetic acid solution under mechanical stirring. The pH of the solution was controlled within 3.5-4.0 with the addition of a 5M NaOH solution. The chitosan solution was then mixed with HNT@PhA in 150 mL of deionized water. To achieve a good dispersion of HNTs, the mixture was mechanically stirred at 550 rpm overnight, and after that, the reaction was continued for 2 hours under ultrasonic treatment at room temperature. The obtained product (labeled as HNT@PhA-CS) was washed with deionized water (obtaining pH<6) and dried at 90 °C for 4h. (See Fig.1) [34].

Figure 1. Modification of halloysite with phytic acid and chitosan

2.3. Preparation of modified-HNT/Polyamide composites

All the polyamide (PA56) composites with pure and modified HNTs were prepared under the same process conditions, using different HNT concentrations (3, 5, 10wt. %) incorporated into PA56. First, the polymer pellets were dried at 110°C for 5h before compounding. Then, they were processed by melt blending in a twin-screw extruder (Brabender Ketsse 20/40 EC, Duisburg, GE) at 260 °C, with a screw speed of 120 rpm. To obtain the standard test samples, the PA56 specimens were further processed by injection molding (Arburg Allrounder 320C, Lossburg, GE) at 265 °C with an injection pressure of 60 bar (See Fig.2).

Figure 2. Typical PA56 samples fabrication process

2.4. Characterization

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was tested on a Nicolet IS50 spectrometer (Waltham, MA, USA) with a wavenumber from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} and 64 scans for every sample. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was conducted on a FEI Talos F200x (FEI Europe B.V. Eindhoven, NL) microscope at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV, the images were recorded by a ceta camera with 4K*4K pixel within the dose rate of 5-30 $\text{e}/\text{\AA}^2\text{s}$. TEM samples were prepared by depositing 10 μL of a dilute ethanol solution in which the particles were evenly dispersed on copper grids. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed with a TA instrument (Q50, New Castle, PA, USA) from 0 to 800 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹. Firstly, the experiments were conducted under nitrogen, and after that under air atmosphere. Melt Flow Index (MFI) was performed by an extrusion plastometer (Kinsgeo KJ-3092, Dongguan, CHN) with a temperature of 280 °C and an applied weight of 2.16 kg. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was made using a TA Q200 instrument (Q200, New Castle, PA, USA). The test was performed under a nitrogen flow of 50 ml/min and the samples were firstly heated to 290 °C at a ramp of 10 °C.min⁻¹. Then, they were cooled to 0 °C and finally heated to 290 °C. Rheology tests were made in a modular compact rheometer: (MCR 702e, Anton Paar, GmbH, Graz, AU) using a frequency sweep measurement over a frequency range of 100-0.1 rads^{-1} at 260 °C. Limiting oxygen index (LOI) was performed with an oxygen index meter (FTT, East Grinstead, UK) according to ASTM D2863-77 standard. The size of the samples was 130 × 6.5 × 3 mm^3 . The vertical burning test was determined with the UL-94 vertical flame chamber (FTT, East Grinstead, UK) using the ASTM D3801-20 standard. The size of the samples was 130 × 13 × 3 mm^3 and IR images were collected with a Fluke Ti480 Infrared camera (Washington, USA).

The extended combustion properties of the samples were determined on a cone calorimeter (FTT, East Grinstead, UK) according to the ISO5660 standard, under a heat flux of 50

kW/m², using a sample size of 100 × 100 × 4 mm³. The scanning electron microscope (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI, Portland, OR, USA) was used for the cross-section and char residue inspections at a voltage of 10.0 kV and 0.69 nA of current. The samples were coated with a conductive layer of gold before SEM observation. Meanwhile, the charring layer was studied by Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw, UK) at room temperature and with 532 nm wavelength. Tensile testing was performed on a universal electromechanical testing machine (INSTRON 3384, Norwood, MA, USA) according to the ISO 527-2 standard at a test speed of 50 mm.min⁻¹, and with a load cell of 2000 N. Charpy impact testing was performed with an impact strength testing machine (Zorn Instruments, Stendal, GE) using a 4 kJ load cell.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of halloysite nanotubes

The TEM images of HNT are shown in Fig 3. A nanotubular structure with open-ended internal lumens was observed. The HNTs were in the range from 200 to 500nm of length, with nanoscale external and internal diameters. After modification, the tubular dimensions of HNTs were nearly identical to the untreated HNTs. However, the observed internal spacing was smaller, indicating that the lumen was filled with organic particles.

Figure 3. TEM Images of (a) pure HNT and (b) HNT@PhA-CS.

The surface morphology of the pure HNTs was investigated by SEM (Fig 4a-c), showing the particle size of the bulk HNTs before modification. The typical EDS elemental mapping was able to detect the fundamental components in both the aluminum and silicate layers of the HNTs. After modification, the phosphorus content increased to almost 14% which was consistent to the initial added amount of phytic acid (HNT-PhA ratio 2:1). The C, O, Al, and Si elements were also obtained during the EDS dispersion and mapping analysis, while the elemental carbon content was remarkably increased after the addition of organic substances such as phytic acid and chitosan.

The FTIR spectra of pure HNT and modified HNT can be seen in Fig. 5a. For the unmodified HNT, the signals at 3694 cm⁻¹, 3619 cm⁻¹, and 910 cm⁻¹ were assigned to the Al-OH stretching and bending vibrations, while the peaks at 1030 cm⁻¹ correspond

to Si-O-Si stretching vibrations [35]. In the phytic acid spectrum, the peaks at 1070 cm^{-1} and 996 cm^{-1} were assigned to the stretching frequencies of the P-O-C groups and the 1637 cm^{-1} signal to the O-P-O stretching vibration [16]. The spectra of pure chitosan exhibited its characteristic peaks at 1637 cm^{-1} and 1609 cm^{-1} representing the deformation vibrations of primary and secondary amine groups and the minor peak at 2920 cm^{-1} was attributed to the C-H band vibration [34]. The modified HNT revealed some typical signals at 1038 cm^{-1} , 3620 cm^{-1} and 3692 cm^{-1} [21]. Additionally, the CS absorption bands at 1067 cm^{-1} , 2920 cm^{-1} , and 2983 cm^{-1} were also observed in the HNT@PhA-CS spectra. There was also a decrease in the 3619 cm^{-1} signal intensity, showing the reduction of HNTs hydroxyl groups after the introduction of the flame retardants. Furthermore, a new signal was found at 1543 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the NH_3^+ vibration, indicating ionic complexation between protonated CS and negatively charged phytic acid [15, 36].

Figure 4. SEM images of pure HNT at different magnifications (a) 100x (b) 500x (c) 1000x (d-e) EDS mapping and (f) Elemental analysis of the HNTs.

The thermal degradation of the HNTs was evaluated by TGA, (Table S1 and Fig. 5b). The unmodified HNT displayed an onset degradation near to $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a total weight loss of 16.2% was observed at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, due to the elimination of interlayer water at first stage and to the removal of hydroxyl groups in HNTs on the second stage of decomposition [37]. The weight loss of HNT@PhA at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was 26% lower than that of pure HNT. The initial degradation of HNT@PhA from $240\text{--}300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ can be related to the release of nonflammable gases during the initial decomposition stage of PhA. Additionally, PhA can be further decomposed at higher temperatures into polyphosphates and catalyze the char formation effect [38]. For HNT@PhA-CS, the weight at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was decreased until 68.9% indicating a 15 wt. % of organic contents in the HNTs. Meanwhile, the onset degradation temperature decreased until $253\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which can be related to the initial decomposition of the electrolyte complex grafted in the external HNT layers. [39].

The particle size analysis was performed to obtain the bulk dimensions of the flame-retardant fillers (Figures 5c, 5d). Additive dispersion through the polyamide matrix is a

significant topic in research, as the potential influence of inorganic particles might directly influence the structural integrity of the composites. Due to the highly active surface area and strong intertubular interactions, the halloysite particles have a strong agglomeration tendency in the bulk size characterizations. Hence, the pure HNT exhibited a standard size of 0.76 μm , while after the introduction of phytic acid in the first step of the reaction, the particle size obtained was 0.92 μm , and for the fillers containing phytic acid and chitosan, there was a slightly larger 1.10 μm particle size obtained due to the incorporation of the chitosan particles into the surface of the HNT.

Figure 5. Characterization results of pure and modified HNTs (a) FTIR (b) TGA in N₂ (c) PSA Differential and (d) PSA Cumulative curves.

3.2. Characterization of modified polyamide composites

3.2.1. Thermal stability

The TGA and DTGA curves of PA56 and modified PA56 composites are shown in Fig. 6, and the corresponding data are listed in Table 1. The pristine PA56 displays a typical single-stage decomposition with the temperature of 5% weight loss (T-5%) and a maximum weight loss (T-Max) at 375 °C and 418 °C, respectively. Almost no char residues were detected (1.3%) at 700 °C due to the extensive degradation of PA56 that sequentially includes the initial cleavage of C-N bonds between the amide groups and its eventual transitions to nitrile by a dehydration process, the removal of carbonyl (C=O) groups, and

finally a larger number of C-C bond breaks when the maximum decomposition temperature is reached [40]. With the incorporation of 3 wt.% HNT and modified HNT into PA56, the T-5%, T-Max and char residue at 700 °C were notably increased. Furthermore, the PA56 composites with higher flame retardant content were able to yield larger char residues at 700 °C, obtaining 12.3% after adding 10 wt.% of the modified HNTs.

Table 1. TGA and DTGA results of PA56 composites

Sample formulation	T _{5wt.%} (°C)		T _{Max} (°C)		Der.W (%/°C)		Residue ^a (%)	
	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂
	PA56	366	375	412	418	2.4	2.6	0.1
PA56+HNT 3%	378	385	425	426	2.0	1.9	3.3	4.1
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	376	382	428	439	2.1	1.9	5.1	5.7
PA56+HNT 5%	369	377	434	437	1.9	1.9	6.3	6.8
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	367	372	431	432	1.9	1.7	8.5	9.4
PA56+HNT 10%	362	369	427	430	1.7	1.6	9.6	10.9
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	359	365	426	429	1.6	1.5	11.2	12.3

Residue^a: Residue weight @700 °C

The increased charring capacity of the PA56/HNT@PhA-CS composites may be mainly due to phytic acid degradation, which enables larger cross-linking sites in the polymer matrix and accelerates the formation of a char layer barrier [33, 37].

Figure 6. (a) TGA and (b) DTGA curves for the pure PA56, and PA56 composites in N₂.

The DSC results shown in Table 2 and Figure 7 were obtained from the first melting and crystallization cycles and the crystallinity degree calculation method is detailed in the supporting information. For pure PA56 a melting temperature of 253.9 °C and a melting enthalpy of 77.6 J/g were related to the crystalline phase of PA56, as previously reported in the literature [41]. A slight decrease in the melting enthalpy was obtained for the PA56 composites, the unmodified HNTs composites with 3 wt.% and 5 wt.% showed a melting enthalpy of 72.6 J/g and 69.9 J/g respectively.

Table 2. DSC results of PA56 composites

Sample formulation	T _m ^a (°C)	T _c ^b (°C)	ΔH _m ^c (J/g)	X _c ^d (%)
PA56	253.9	216.4	77.6	41.3
PA56+HNT 3%	253.8	215.8	72.6	38.6
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	253.9	215.1	71.3	37.9
PA56+HNT 5%	253.1	214.6	69.9	37.1
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	253.2	214.0	64.2	34.1
PA56+HNT 10%	253.4	213.7	61.1	32.5
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	253.2	212.6	60.7	32.1

T_m^a: Melting temperature, T_c^b: Crystallization temperature, ΔH_m^c: Melting Enthalpy, X_c^d: Degree of crystallinity

Meanwhile, the samples containing phytic acid and chitosan showed a lower enthalpy of 71.3 and 64.2 J/g, indicating that the addition of the PhA-CS complex leads to the absorption of lower amounts of heat during the melting cycle of the composites. The crystallization of PA56 was also limited by the addition of HNT, indicating a higher fraction of amorphous phase and lower chain mobility after the FR addition.

Figure 7. DSC test results (a) 1st Heating cycle and (b) cooling cycle curves for the pure and modified PA56 samples.

3.2.2. Rheological properties

The MFI measurements are shown in Fig. 8a and Table 3. The addition of solid particles into a polymer matrix usually leads to lower MFI values as a result of the hindered fluidity of the polymer segments after the flame retardant addition. In this study, the MFI value of pure PA56 was 12.2 g/10min and due to the larger content of solid particles, the MFI results of the PA56 composites were notably decreased to 6.8 g/10min, indicating that the melt flow capacity of the composites is highly sensitive to the concentration of HNT filler. Meanwhile, in the complex viscosity (η^*) measurements (fig. 8b), the composites exhibited a similar rheological response, obtaining a gradual decrease of η^* as the frequency increased.

Table 3. MFI of PA56 and its composites

Sample formulation	MFI (g/10min)
PA56	12.2 ± 0.2
PA56+HNT 3%	9.6 ± 0.1
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	9.1 ± 0.4
PA56+HNT 5%	8.3 ± 0.3
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	8.8 ± 0.2
PA56+HNT 10%	6.8 ± 0.4
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	7.5 ± 0.5

The effects of filler incorporation were also observed since the viscosity of the PA56 was increased at low and high frequencies after the addition of the HNTs, indicating the reduction of the melting-like behavior as the HNTs concentrations were increased.

Figure 8. (a) MFI (b) complex viscosity curves of the pure and modified PA56 samples.

3.2.3. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of PA56 and its composites are presented in Table 4 and the corresponding curves in Fig. 9 (a-d). The PA56 Control sample showed a tensile strength value of 72.1 MPa and the elongation at break result was 5.4%, revealing a brittle fracture behavior. The introduction of flame retardants frequently generates inevitable decline to the mechanical performance of polymers. However, in the presence of low loadings of HNTs (e.g. 3, 5 wt.%), the tensile strength was increased to 80.5 MPa, and the elongation at break was also increased to 7.2%. Meanwhile, at higher concentrations of HNTs, the agglomeration and overloading of fillers resulted in poor compatibility between PA56 and the HNTs, affecting the stability of the polyamide structural framework. More researchers have paid attention to the strength preservation of polyamide products after flame retardant treatment, but a significant loss of elongation is frequently observed after increasing the concentration of FR. [33, 37]. In this work, PA56 containing 3 and 5 wt. % of the HNTs imparted comprehensive mechanical improvements to the PA56.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of PA56 composites

Sample formulation	TS ^a (MPa)	EB ^b (%)	YM ^c (MPa)	Charpy Strength (kJ/m ²)	
				Notched	Unnotched
PA56	72.1±0.8	5.4±0.1	1624±12	15.6±0.3	NB
PA56+HNT 3%	78.1±1.2	5.9±0.4	2122±25	15.9±0.9	NB
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	80.5±3.1	6.7±0.3	2347±37	16.3±0.2	NB
PA56+HNT 5%	74.5±0.9	5.7±0.3	1922±26	13.3±0.2	14.8±0.3
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	76.6±2.1	7.2±0.2	2016±52	13.9±0.1	14.9±0.5
PA56+HNT 10%	67.8±0.8	6.3±0.2	1152±21	11.1±0.1	12.4±0.3
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	70.7±1.2	6.1±0.1	1583±42	11.8±0.3	13.0±0.1

TS^a: Tensile strength, EB^b: Elongation at break, YM^c: Young's Modulus, *NB: Sample not broken

The Charpy impact test results are shown in Fig. 9b, the impact strength of the notched PA56 samples was 15.6 kJ/m², after the incorporation of 3 wt.% of the pure HNT, the impact strength was slightly increased to 15.9 kJ/m² and it was further increased to 16.3 kJ/m² with the 3 wt.% of the modified HNTs. Meanwhile, the addition of higher amounts of the HNTs (5, 10 wt.%) caused a decrease in the impact strength of the composites. The samples with 10 wt.% of the pure and modified HNTs obtained a result of 11.1 and 11.8 kJ/m² respectively. The unnotched samples exhibited a similar performance as the pure PA56 and the 3wt.% samples were not broken after receiving the pendulum impact. All the samples with 5 and 10 wt.% of HNTs also showed the same decreasing trend, indicating that the impact strength was dramatically affected by the limited capacity of the FR fillers to form stable structural interactions with the polyamide matrix at higher concentrations.

Figure 9. (a) Tensile stress-strain curves (b) Charpy impact strength (c) Storage modulus and (d) Tan delta curves of the pure and modified PA56 samples.

The dynamic mechanical properties such as storage modulus and phase angle tangent (Tan Delta) were recorded as a function of temperature in a heating cycle from -100°C to 100°C, the results are presented in Fig. 9(c-d), all the samples exhibited two different regions separated by the tan delta peaks which correspond to the β -relaxation around -80 °C that is normally related to the motion of non-hydrogen bonded amide groups and water molecules bonded to carbonyl groups, while the larger peaks detected between 40-80°C were assigned to the dynamic glass transition (α -relaxation) corresponding to the motion of aliphatic segments of polyamide [42]. Fig. 9c shows the storage modulus decrease from low temperature to high temperature, especially at the temperature corresponding to the dynamic relaxation transition. It was found that the storage modulus of the PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 3wt.% sample was notably increased compared to the value of PA56 in both the glassy and rubbery regions. In other words, the PA56 exhibited higher deformation resistance and energy dissipation ability in the ambient temperature range until 80 °C after the modification with the HNT@PhA-CS. In addition, the loss factor (Tan delta) showed a slightly shift to higher temperature at the presence of 3 wt.% of pure and modified HNTs, indicating the reduced mobility of the PA56 phase at a low temperature range after the incorporation of the inorganic particles. [43]

Figure 10. SEM cross-section images of (a) Pure PA56 (b) PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 3% (c) PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 5% and (d) PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 10%.

The SEM inspection of the polymer composites' fracture surface is extensively used to understand the effects of filler addition to a polyamide matrix. The SEM micrographs that exhibited a more uniform dispersion of the HNTs within the matrix where those with 3wt.% of FR content (fig. 10b), several micro-sized radial fracture stripes were observed in the cross-section of the 5wt.% samples (fig. 10c) and finally, for the highly HNT filled composites (fig. 10d), the size of the cracks was larger and a higher surface layer displacement was also observed, the increased filler content caused the polyamide to exhibit a higher degree of brittle fracture. As illustrated previously, nanocomposites (with

3wt.% of HNT) exhibited improved mechanical performance compared with pure PA56, showing the coexistence of a more dispersed surface morphology with smaller HNT aggregates [34].

3.2.4. Flame retardancy

The fire performance of PA56 composites was initially studied by LOI and UL-94 tests, the corresponding results are presented in Table 5 and Fig. 11(a-d). The control PA56 sample was easily ignited obtaining a LOI value of 26.8% combined with a V-2 result in the UL-94 test due to the severe melt dripping. The LOI values gradually increased along with the amount of HNTs.

Table 5. LOI and UL-94 test results of PA56 composites

Sample formulation	LOI (%)	UL-94 (Thickness: 3.2 mm)				
		t1 (s)	t2 (s)	Dripping	Ignition	Rating
PA56	26.8	11±2	17±3	High	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT 3%	29.7	7±3	18±6	High	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	29.9	9±2	15±4	High	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT 5%	31.4	5±1	12±3	High	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	31.8	3±5	9±3	Low	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT 10%	32.4	5±2	9±1	Low	Yes	V-2
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	33.5	2±4	7±2	Low	No	V-0

The samples containing pure HNTs (3 and 5 wt.%) were able to reach the LOI values of 29.7 and 31.4 respectively, but unfortunately, the melt dripping performance of the samples was quite high, causing the ignition of the cotton below the sample. The samples containing 5 wt.% of the modified HNTs were able to reduce the previously described dripping issue and the combustion times significantly, obtaining a V-2 rating as the underneath cotton was still able to produce a small flaming. At last, by the presence of 10 wt.% of HNT@PhA-CS, the LOI value arrived at 33.5% and the UL-94 test produced a V-0 grade with an important reduction of melt dripping. The combustion process of dripping polymeric materials during the vertical burning test can be divided into 3 main steps, (1) Contact phase: the flame appears on the surface of the sample followed by a temperature increase. (2) Middle flame phase: the polymer is consumed by the fire and temperature increases with more production of flammable particles feeding gas phase of the combustion. (3) End flame phase: the flame disappears or reaches the holding clamp after enveloping the sample [44]. IR images presented in Fig. 11(b-d) reflect the different temperature zones of the composites after removing the flame application in the first ignition of the vertical burning test and the testing configuration is presented in Fig S6. The intensive combustion of the control sample (Fig. 11b) produced a high temperature of 528 °C and 11s of burning time after the flame removal.

The addition of the HNTs caused a decrease in the surface temperature until 293°C and 277°C while the burning times were also significantly decreased to 5s and 2s for the composites with the 10 wt.% of the pure and modified HNTs respectively, which was in agreement with the previously described LOI indicators showing an enhanced self-extinguish capacity.

Figure 11. (a) LOI and (b) IR image of Pure PA56 (c) PA56+HNT 10% (d) PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%

The fire performance was evaluated by cone calorimeter test, the heat and smoke release curves were shown in Fig. 12, and several key results were summarized in Table 6. The combustion of pristine PA56 is intense and fast, yielding a peak heat release rate (pHRR, Fig. 12a) of 863 kw/m². The final residue of 0.6 wt.% reveals the almost complete burning of the test samples. As described in previous research, the introduction of nanotubes with suitable dispersion capacity within polymeric chains could produce a more compact framework, which inhibits heat and smoke release [21, 45]. Hence, the heat release of the composites was significantly reduced, and the combustion times were delayed by more than 100s after the addition of the HNTs. The introduction of HNT@PhA-CS further reduced the heat release, and the samples displayed a wide plateau after ignition, which is characteristic of char-forming materials, indicating that the presence of pure or modified HNT increases the charring capacity of the PA56 matrix.

The total smoke production (TSP, Fig. 12c) was decreased after the addition of 3 wt.% of the pure HNT and HNT@PhA-CS, but for the 5 wt.% samples the TSP was slightly higher than that of PA56, the decomposition of phytic acid and chitosan during burning released some inert gas, which increased the value of TSP. The release of toxic gases, such as CO, was delayed and decreased, which is important in a real fire scenario. Among the tested samples, PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 10 wt.% shows the lowest pHRR (decreased by 51% compared to pure PA56) and longest burning time. Besides the enhanced charring effect, which was confirmed by the increased residues (Fig. 12d), the physical barrier effect of the protective char layer also represents an essential feature of nanocomposites based on the non-charring PA56 polymer matrix [46, 47].

Table 6. Cone calorimetry results of PA56 composites

Sample formulation	TTI (s)	pHRR (kW/m ²)	pHRR Red.(%)	THR (MJ/m ²)	TSP (m ²)	Residue wt.(%)
PA56	61±2	863±14	-	150±7	15.1±5	0.6±0.2
PA56+HNT 3%	68±4	714±16	18	136±8	12.8±2	5.3±1.1
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 3%	67±3	624±15	28	132±14	12.3±4	6.8±0.9
PA56+HNT 5%	66±3	604±12	30	135±12	16.7±7	7.1±0.3
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 5%	62±2	580±16	33	130±14	15.2±6	8.6±0.6
PA56+HNT 10%	58±2	464±7	46	132±9	14.1±5	11.1±1.5
PA56+HNT@PhA-CS 10%	51±4	419±10	51	129±5	17.7±9	13.2±0.8

The times to ignition (TTI) of PA56 were delayed upon the addition of 3 and 5 wt.% of the HNTs, but after the addition of 10 wt.% of the modified HNTs, the ignition times were decreased along with increasing the flame-retardant concentration, reasonably due to the catalytic effect of the acid sites contained in the modified HNTs [15]. The shortest TTI was observed in the PA56/HNT@PhA-CS 10 wt.%, suggesting the modification with the PhA-CS complex also enhances the catalytic effect of HNT during PA56 degradation. With the addition of HNT to PA56, there is a decrease of THR (Fig. 16b) and the decrease becomes more significant when the modified HNTs were used confirming the influential role of P and N in the flame retardancy of PA56 composites [37].

Figure 12. (a) Peak heat release rate (b) Total heat release (c) total smoke production and (d) Weight curves of the pure PA56 and PA56 composites.

3.2.5. Condensed phase analysis

To obtain more information about the morphology of the char layers, digital images were recorded for PA56 and its composites with 10 wt.% of HNTs (fig. 13a-c). For pure PA56 there was a little residue found after the burning indicating the free and almost complete combustion cycle of the polyamide chains. For sample PA56 + HNT, there was a thin char layer with obvious cracks on the surface, suggesting that even the pure nanomaterials were able to yield a small layer of char during the burning. For PA56 + HNT@PhA-CS, the charring performance was enhanced significantly, obtaining a larger- sized barrier with smaller cracks. The surface morphology and microstructure of the residues after cone calorimetry were also investigated by SEM (Fig. 13d-f), and it was observed that the char morphologies were consistent with the HRR results, where the composites exhibited a small char residue after the pure nanoclay addition. However, the presence of big cracks and holes suggests the char layer was not compact enough to contain the escape of combustible matter produced in the burning process. As for the residue of the HNT@PhA-CS sample, a continuous intumescent char layer was formed, which was relatively dense and had fewer cavities. Hence, the flame retardancy of the PA56 composites was notably enhanced with a more stable char layer (containing Al, Si, C, and P) acting as a more efficient heat shielding to protect the polyamide matrix.

Figure 13. (a-c) Digital images (d-f) SEM image and elemental analysis (g-i) Raman spectra of char residues

EDS analysis was performed to study the elemental composition of the residues obtained after the cone calorimeter test (Fig. 13d-f). The char of the pure PA56 was composed only of carbon and oxygen. The char of sample PA56 + HNT was formed by C, O, Al and Si, revealing that the residue was a brittle carbonaceous char from the degraded PA56 material with a small amount of aluminosilicate residue from the undegraded HNT [45]. A lower concentration of carbon, aluminum and oxygen, but higher amount of silicon and a low phosphorus content were observed in the PA56 + HNT@PhA-CS sample. It is considered that in the presence of the PhA-CS complex, the flame-retardant substances coated in the surface of the halloysite nanomaterials were able to accelerate the carbon layer production and further improve the performance of the condensed phase mechanism. Moreover, the synergistic effect of P and N also promoted the hardening of the Al, Si-containing barrier layer. Leading to a more efficient heat shielding and improving the flame retardancy. The pyrolysis of phytic acid normally produces polyphosphate and phosphorus-based acids such as phosphoric acid, that can dehydrate and carbonize oxygen-containing polymer materials, creating a dense carbonaceous layer that effectively isolates the release of oxygen and heat [49].

Raman spectra of the carbon residues were obtained to further explore the in-plane microcrystalline dimensions of the carbon based residues (Fig. 13g-i). All of the Raman spectra exhibit two visible D and G bands that are related to the vibration of carbon atoms in disordered graphite (D-band) and to the vibration of sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms in the graphite layer (G-band) [10, 32]. I_D/I_G ratio could approximately indicate the carbonization degree of the residues. Higher I_D/I_G ratio value indicates a smaller degree of graphitic carbonization in the material. It is accepted that with a lower I_D/I_G ratio of integrated intensities of D and G bands, a higher graphitic carbon degree and a denser char layer are obtained [51, 52]. Hence, the I_D/I_G ratio-value follows the sequence PA56 > PA56 + HNT > PA56 + HNT@PhA-CS. This evidence indicates that after modification, the HNTs were able to yield a more compact residue containing more ordered graphite-like carbon, which was induced by the catalytic charring action of the PhA-CS complex [53].

3.2.6. Gas phase analysis

Real-time TGA-FTIR was carried out to study the nature of the volatile gases produced during the combustion of the samples. Data comparability was ensured by using samples with nearly identical mass to perform the tests. Several FTIR absorption peaks were selected to track their intensity change through time. As shown in Fig. 14, the typical carbon monoxide and dioxide peaks were found on both the spectrum of PA56 and PA56 + HNT@PhA-CS: the signals at 2195 and 2363 cm^{-1} , were observed in both the onset and peak degradation spectra and further assigned to the stretching vibration of CO and to the asymmetrical stretching of CO₂ respectively [38].

Figure 14. TGA-FTIR Results of the pure PA56 and PA56/HNT@PhA-CS

Other symbolic signals such as the alkanes or alkyl substituents stretching signals at 2938 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CH}_3$) and 2783 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CH}_2-$) were also observed [54-56]. The peak at 1755 cm^{-1} indexed as the vibration of carbonyl groups showed slightly higher intensity in the modified HNTs sample, indicating the interactions with the organic segments of the phytic acid-chitosan complex. The P-O-C vibration signal was detected 963 cm^{-1} and N-H bending signal was also found at 1625 cm^{-1} , revealing the quenching effect of phosphorus-containing fragments and diluting effect of non-flammable gases. The absorption peaks at 3339 cm^{-1} assigned to the PA56 pyrolysis products, showed an evident lower intensity on the spectrum of the volatiles of PA56/HNT@PhA-CS in contrast to that of pure PA56. Confirming that after the incorporation of the PhA-CS complex, the release of the gas fragments was inhibited, thus reducing the generation of fuels [32]. Meanwhile, as the phosphorus and nitrogen contents were increased, the transfer of heat and oxygen towards the flaming zones was effectively reduced, delaying the release of combustible particles as well. Therefore, PhA-CS complex enabled gas phase activity through the release of nitrogen and phosphate fragments into the combustion zones, in order to hinder the combustion and assist the charring of the halloysite in the polyamide framework.

3.2.7. Flame retardant mechanism

Based on the previous discussion, a possible flame retardant and smoke suppression mechanisms of HNT@PhA-CS are proposed. By the combination of inorganic HNTs and organic phytic acid-chitosan complex, the flame retardant system can form a network structure of chemical crosslinking in the PA56 matrix and impart flame retardant action in both the gas and condensed phase, being the condensed phase the principal mechanism [33]. In detail, phytic acid is first degraded to generate phosphoric acid, which works as an acidic catalyst, resulting in lower TTI values [57, 58]. Moreover, the reaction of phosphoric acid and HNTs could form silicon-alumino-phosphate, which can promote the crosslinking and condensation of chitosan molecules, increasing the char strength. This is confirmed by the band at 1089 cm^{-1} in Fig. 14 [33, 59].

Figure 15. Proposed combustion mechanism scheme of pure PA56 and PA56/HNT@PhA-CS

Furthermore, HNTs provided key contribution by holding decomposition products in their tubular structures. Especially after modification, the HNTs were properly dispersed in PA56 matrix and more flammable particles were trapped in the internal layers during the combustion [33]. Meanwhile, the surface of HNTs was also coated by charring agents, resulting in enhanced barrier effects [60]. In the gas phase, the PO• and HPO• radicals released from phytic acid exhibited flame inhibition effect by capturing active H• and OH•, while non-combustible gases such as CO₂, H₂O, and NH₃ released from the chitosan molecules contained in the PhA-CS complex were able dilute the concentration of fuel and reduce combustion intensity. [61, 62]. Then, the surface oxygen concentration decreased, and the flame was inhibited by the synergistic action of HNT@PhA-CS that successfully hindered the free radical chain reaction, notably improving the performance of PA56 composites against the fire.

4. Conclusions

A biobased flame retardant halloysite containing phytic acid and chitosan was prepared successfully by the combination of phytic acid and halloysite via ionic exchange reaction and the addition of chitosan molecules by the PEC formation in a 2-step reaction method. After the addition of the HNTs into PA56, the mechanical properties showed enhanced performance, especially at low concentrations (3-5 wt. %). The tensile strength and elongation at break were increased by 12% and 20%, respectively, compared with the control sample (pure PA56). Meanwhile, the tensile strength of the composites was slightly decreased at higher HNTs content (10 wt. %). The nanocomposites also achieved important improvements in the flame-retardant properties, the LOI values of HNT@PhA-CS reached 33.5% (for the samples with 10wt.% of the modified HNTs) with a UL-94 rating of V-0. The pHRR from the cone calorimeter test was decreased by 51 % and the final residue was increased by 13% as a result of the catalytic carbonization and the formation of a char barrier with a more compact structure. The flame retardancy enhancements provided by this system were assigned to different mechanisms mainly based on the phosphorus and nitrogen addition to the HNT nanomaterials and their further influence as an efficient physical

barrier and heat shield during combustion, supported by the contribution of the fuel dilution and flame inhibition effects in the gas phase. The aforementioned results demonstrate the potential of phytic acid and chitosan as biobased flame retardants for improving the biobased polyamide composites' main features (thermal stability, fire safety, and mechanical properties) without compromising their sustainability, allowing polyamides to maintain their level as one of the most demanded polymers in the engineering industry.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Jose Hobson: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Guang-Zhong Yin:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Xiang Ao:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Mingyang Zhang:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Juan Pedro Fernández-Blázquez:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **De-Yi Wang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doiXXXXXXXX>.

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